

SUB-CRITICAL DAMAGE IN GLASS-FIBRE /EPOXY-RESIN LAMINATES: USE OF LASER DIFFRACTION AND CLSM TECHNIQUES.

Bee Li MOK-YEO [Singapore Polytechnic]

Michael G Bader

Department of Materials Science & Engineering
University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH, UK

ABSTRACT

Sub-critical damage of microscopic dimensions has been studied in transparent glass-fibre/epoxy-resin laminates using a laser diffraction technique, the confocal laser scanning microscope and conventional light microscopy. Damage, in the form of micro-debonds at the fibre/matrix interface, has been observed to initiate, in transverse plies subjected to tension, at strains of the order of 0.2%. The laser and CLSM techniques have been shown to be useful for monitoring damage in these transparent laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Sub-critical damage in composite laminates may be defined as observable micro-scale fracture processes which do not result in complete failure. Several such processes have been identified: These are summarised in Table 1. and those of interest in the present work are shown schematically in fig 1.

Matrix cracking in the 90° ply of sandwich and multi-ply laminates subjected to monotonic loading in tension has been extensively studied [1-3], and it has been established that the first cracks are formed at a strain, ϵ_c , which is characteristic of the laminate constitution, configuration and processing history. In [0,90]_s E-glass-fibre/epoxy-resin laminates, ϵ_c is typically in the range 0.3 - 0.4%. It is influenced strongly by the absolute and relative thicknesses of the 0° and 90° plies and also by any thermally induced residual strains, which are usually tensile in the 90° plies in the direction parallel to the 0° fibres. Other factors which influence ϵ_c are the properties of the resin, the state of cure and the strength of the fibre/matrix interface. In both glass/epoxy [GRFP] and carbon-fibre/epoxy [CFRP] systems these transverse ply matrix cracks are most frequently observed to follow the fibre/matrix interface. But it is very difficult to observe the exact point of initiation. There is considerable evidence [4,5] that initiation occurs towards the centre of the 90° ply and the crack then propagates outwards in both directions towards the adjacent 0° plies. A number of workers [4,6] have attempted to identify the process by which the cracks are initiated and both interface (4a in Table 1) and matrix (4b) cracks have been observed to form at strains a little lower than ϵ_c , or in areas between fully formed cracks. This type of damage is sub-critical in the sense that it does not lead to catastrophic failure under tensile loading. However, it does seriously

reduce the compression strength of a laminate and, since this is often the more critical performance factor, it is often used as the basis for defining "failure". This *first-ply-failure* (FPF) criterion is generally conservative.

The concept that some damage processes might operate at strains *lower* than ϵ_c arose, when it was observed that matrix cracks would eventually form in laminates subjected to cyclic strains significantly lower than ϵ_c . This is clearly of practical concern since it could lead to the imposition of even lower allowable strains than the FPF criterion. There are other

Table 1. Sub-Critical Damage Processes in Composite Laminates

Type of Laminate	Loading	Observed Damage
Uniaxial	0° Tension 0° Compression	1. Sporadic fibre fracture 2. Matrix cracking normal to fibres. 3. Fibre kinking [micro-buckling]
[0,90] _s sandwich	0° Tension	4a. Matrix micro-cracking - debond at F/M interface. 4b. Matrix initiated micro-cracking. 5a. Interply delamination. 5b. Intraply delamination. 6. Splitting in 0° plies.
[0, ±45,90] _s various sequences	0° Tension 0° Compression	4a. in 90° & 45° plies 4b. in 90° & 45° plies 5a. in 90° ply 5b. between 0/90 and/or 45/90 plies 6. Splitting in 0° plies 5b. between 0/90 and/or 45/90 plies
[0, ±45,90] _s various sequences	Impact normal to plane of lamination	4a. as for tension above 4b. ditto 5b. ditto 6. ditto

manifestations of low strain damage phenomena: Manders et al [4] and Bailey and Parvizi [2] reported "strain whitening" and "damage healing" in glass-fibre/epoxy-resin laminates and these processes were further studied by Nensi [7] who also observed colour changes when a cross-ply E-glass-fibre/epoxy-resin laminate was extended in tension. These phenomena were attributed to the formation of cracks or debonds of dimensions which would lead to the observed optical phenomena. The whitening and colour change, from blue to pink under oblique illumination, were partially reversible when the strains were relaxed. Furthermore, if the sample was strained to the point of transverse cracking in the central 90° ply, it was observed that both whitening and the colour change were reversed in a narrow band either side of the crack. This was considered to be a zone in the central ply where the strain had relaxed following the formation of a transverse crack. This is in accordance with the established shear transfer theories for transverse cracking [4]. If a specimen, which had been strained sufficiently

Figure 1. Sub-critical damage in 90° ply.

to cause intense whitening, was unloaded and then annealed at about 100 °C for a short time the damage appeared to "repair". However, fully formed transverse cracks did not repair. This may be explained on the basis that in the case of micro-cracks they close completely when the strain is relaxed allowing diffusion processes to partially or fully reunite the two surfaces. In the case of larger cracks the surface topology is too complex and additionally fracture debris prevent perfect closure. The key features of these phenomena are illustrated schematically in fig 2. Nensi [7] also conducted a few experiments using a HeNe laser to measure the light scattering from these features and also observed a diffraction effect.

The present work has been directed towards the observation of the earliest manifestations of damage in the 90° ply of sandwich laminates extended in tension. The model laminate is an optically transparent E-glass/epoxy and it has been studied using an optical laser diffraction technique [8,9], developed from Nensi's original work, and the confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM).

STRESS WHITENING IN CROSS-PLYED GRP LAMINATES

Figure 2.

EXPERIMENTAL

The laminates were fabricated from single, 600 tex rovings of an E-glass fibre (Silenka 084 M19 600 EC15). The mean diameter of the individual filaments was $15.7 \mu\text{m}$. The resin was formulated from a standard difunctional bisphenol-A based epoxy resin (Stag Epoxide 300), cured with 60 phr nadic-methyl-anhydride (NMA) using 4 phr of a proprietary tertiary amine accelerator (Stag K61B). This formulation has low viscosity and has been found to infiltrate a tightly packed array of glass fibre to produce a virtually pore-free laminate with a high level of transparency. It is a pale amber colour as cured and darkens a little on post-curing (this was omitted in the present work in order maintain maximum transparency). The glass roving was wound onto a square "window frame" support to form a $0^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ$ sequence of uniaxial fibre arrays. The region in the middle of the frame was then vacuum infiltrated with the liquid resin, pressed between two glass plates (suitably treated with a mould release system) and then cured in an oven at 100°C , whilst constrained by dead weights. (The details of this technique have been discussed elsewhere [4]). The finished plate is approximately 250 mm square and 1.5 mm thick. A 0.5 mm central 90° ply between a pair of 0.5 mm, 0° outer plies. The fibres are well wetted and impregnated so that the individual rovings in the transparent laminate cannot be discerned by the naked eye. A uniaxial plate of similar dimensions was also made so that the basic lamina properties could be observed.

Figure 3. Laser diffraction set-up.

Parallel sided coupon specimens, 230 x 10 and 20 mm, were cut from the laminates, the free edges were polished, to remove any stress raising defects and also to allow the edges to be examined microscopically. A number of tensile tests were conducted to establish the basic mechanical properties and to observe the development of transverse cracking in the 90° ply. Further specimens were extended in tension and the laser diffraction patterns observed. The set up for the diffraction experiment is shown schematically in fig 3. The specimen is set up vertically in the tensile testing machine in the normal manner. The beam from a HeNe laser is directed horizontally, normal to the plane of the laminate, to shine through the specimen. The diffraction pattern is observed on a fine ground glass screen set 190 mm from the specimen. The laser used was of 0.8 mW power and produced a 0.48 mm diameter beam of coherent light with a wavelength of 633 nm. The patterns were recorded at appropriate strain intervals using a 35 mm camera set up behind the ground glass screen. Measurements of the intensity of the pattern were obtained by scanning a photo-diode detector vertically and horizontally across the diffracted beam and recording the strength of the signal (mV). A number of tests were interrupted at various levels of strain so that the specimens could be examined by conventional optical microscopy and by the CLSM. The latter technique is especially appropriate in that it can be focused below the surface of the specimen to observe features within the interior.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fibre fraction (V_f) in the [0,90,0] laminate was measured and found to be 0.52. A typical pair of curves of stress vs longitudinal and transverse strain is shown in fig 4 and the development of transverse cracking with strain in fig 5. The secant modulus at 0.25% strain was 20.6 GPa and Poisson's ratio 0.22. The stress/longitudinal strain curve is virtually linear to a strain of 0.3%, when there is a slight "knee", further more pronounced knees are observed at strains of 0.4 and 0.7% by which strain the tangent modulus has fallen to less than a third of its original level. The knee at 0.3% strain was associated with the observation of the formation of "white bands" across the specimen. These are areas of a "milky" translucency which are attributed [4,7] to the formation of light-scattering defects within the 90° ply of the laminate. The more pronounced knee at 0.4% strain coincides with the observation of the formation of the first transverse crack. These cracks continue to form, and the crack density (fig 5) increases, right up to a strain of just over 1.5% when the test was discontinued. There was no particular feature associated with the knee at 0.7%, but care must be exercised when attempting to correlate the stress/strain and damage/strain curves since the strain is measured over only 10 mm of the gauge length, whilst cracks are counted over a 50 mm length. The measured strain may be anomalous when a transverse crack occurs immediately under the strain gauge.

Figure 4. Stress/strain curve for [0,90,0] sandwich laminate.

Figure 5. Plot of transverse crack density vs. strain.

The laser experiment produces a Fraunhofer diffraction pattern. Initial experiments showed that a uniaxial coupon (fibres vertical) gave rise to a horizontal pattern (x-band), intense at the centre and diminishing outwards. The visible width was about 40 mm using the set up described. Very little change in the pattern was observed, fig 6, as the axial strain was increased up to 0.6%. A 90° uniaxial laminate (fibres horizontal) produced a vertical pattern (y-band) of similar appearance, as expected, but broadened from ≈ 40 mm to ≈ 100 mm as the strain was increased up to 0.5% (when the specimen failed). The precise optical mechanism of this diffraction is not yet understood and is the subject of future work. It is clear, however, that strain normal to the fibre axis increases the width of the vertical band, due either to the increased separation of the fibres or to the development of light-scattering cracks, or to both effects.

The pattern from the cross plied laminate was a cross. On extension the width of the x-band was observed to decrease slightly, whilst the y-band increased sharply over the strain range 0.2 - 0.5%. This is shown clearly in fig 7. The decrease in width of the x-band (due to the 0°

Figure 6. Diffraction band width vs. strain for 0° and 90° laminates.

Figure 7. Diffraction band width vs. strain for [0,90,0] laminate.

plies) is attributed to the interaction between the plies which would result in a small negative strain being induced in the transverse direction of the longitudinal plies (Poisson effect). The sharp increase in the y-band and the appearance of additional "cross bars", fig 8, is due to both strain and damage development in the 90° ply. The plot of the ratio of x to y band widths, fig 9, correlates well with the observation of whitening and transverse cracking. It is noteworthy that the threshold of "damage" detection is at about 0.2% strain which is lower than the strain at which whitening is first observed. This suggests that damage processes initiate this very low level of strain.

The CLSM observations showed that there were some light-scattering defects in both 0° and 90° plies of the unstrained laminate. These were mainly small circular features < 10 μm in diameter. They are thought to be at points of contact between fibres, especially at the interface between the 0° and 90° plies. This is shown schematically in fig 10. They are possibly regions of inadequate resin infiltration and wetting. As the strain is increased to 0.2%, rows of these features are observed together with some "lines", in the fibre direction, in both 0° and 90° plies. By the time the strain has been increased to 0.3% a high density of these line features, spaced typically at 20 - 50 μm intervals in both directions was observed. A layer of circular features (delaminations) was also observed at the junction between the 0° and 90° plies.

Figure 8. Typical diffraction patterns for the [0,90,0] laminate at strains of 0.15% and 0.5%

Figure 9. A plot of the ratio of the y to x diffraction band widths for the [0,90,0] laminate

Conventional reflected light microscopy of the polished specimen edge showed that small debonds were formed, in the 90° ply, at the fibre/matrix interface. These were in the form of arcs, of length (in the ply thickness direction) typically half the fibre diameter. They would extend over a much longer distance into the ply, but it was not possible to measure this. At strains of 0.3% the density of these debonds had increased and some had coalesced to form microcracks, which are undoubtedly the nuclei of the transverse cracks which form at strains of above 0.4%.

CONCLUSIONS

There is considerable evidence of the development of sub-critical damage at strains as low as 0.2% in a [0,90,0] E-glass-fibre/epoxy-resin laminate. The damage might originate at points of fibre-to-fibre contact, or in inadequately infiltrated regions of the laminate. Two types of early damage have been observed: Debonds in the 90° ply at the fibre/matrix interface, oriented normal to the direction of extension, and micro-delaminations at points of contact between fibres in the 0° and 90° plies. The debonds are observed to develop into full transverse cracks but, under the monotonic extension used, the micro-delaminations did not develop to diameters more than about 10 μm. The laser diffraction and CLSM techniques have both proved to be effective for the observation of this fine-scale damage. However, it must be emphasised that both techniques are only applicable to highly transparent materials.

MICRO-DELAMINATION AT POINTS OF FIBRE CONTACT

Figure 10. Schematic of the micro-delaminations at fibre crossovers observed in the CLSM

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